

FEEDBACK ASSOCIATED WITH THE CORRECTION TO ERRORS WITHIN THE TASKS

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ABSTRACT

Teachers' beliefs are noteworthy topic for researchers because of the input they supply for the improvement of English language teaching and learning. Teachers' beliefs have a deep impact on their classroom principles. The realization of this relationship is incredibly vital for academics to arrange and implement their new syllabus. Teachers' beliefs have an effect on what they accomplish in their classroom, their attitudes, and their learner' beliefs. They guide teachers to adopt their teaching ways for addressing their teaching challenges, form language learners' learning surroundings, their motivation and their language ability. During this study, the researchers outline the term belief, justify the characters of teachers' beliefs, express sources of teachers' beliefs, and at last mention some previous studies on teachers' beliefs.

Based on the assumption above considerations teacher's self-confidence will not only be targeted for the personal development however stabilizes the learner's skills and I can assure that teacher's feedback on related tasks obviously demonstrates its productivity in the class. As Zamell said in 1981 "The teacher's output becomes the input for the student and determines future performance and therefore student's output becomes the input for the teacher and determines the reaction to that performance. Teaching and learning aren't any longer exclusive roles, they become the provinces of both performers within the classroom: whereas the teacher instructs, teacher learns about what must be done next and while the learner learns, the student gives instruction about what information is lacking.

Introduction

Feedback studies tend to point out terribly high effects on learning. However, conjointly incorporates a terribly high effects and a few studies show that feedback will have negative effects and make things worse. It is therefore vital to understand the potential benefits and the

possible limitations of feedback as a teaching and learning approach. In general, research-based approaches that explicitly aim to provide feedback to learners. Problems are likely to arise if there is a mismatch between the role perceptions of learners and teachers. According to Breen and Candlin (1980) the teacher has three

main roles in the communicative classroom. The first is to act as a facilitator of the communicative process, the second is to act as a participant and the third is to act as an observer and learner. If the learners see the teacher as someone who should be providing explicit instructions and modelling of the target language and the teacher sees him or herself as a facilitator then conflict can arise. On this regards the teacher's modelling appropriate feedback to the learner and guide them through the task is crucial to build soft contact between them.

The language of feedback refers to the responses given by the teacher to what learners produce in the classroom . In it's most narrow definition, this refers to teacher response to error.

Feedback is the information that is given to the learner concerning his or her performance of a learning task typically with the target of improving this performance, some examples in pedagogy the words "Yes right!" said to a learner who has answered the question.

Most teachers are aware of feedback in terms of its motivational value -the value of positive feedback-the value of positive feedback and the dis-incentive that negative reinforcement can produce. However apart from the motivational aspects of providing feedback, there are linguistic and cognitive reasons for teachers to consider closely how they respond. The precise content of the teacher response as it relates to the learner's production may well have an important influence on the learning process.

Discussion

Feedback has two main distinguishable components: assesment and correction. In assesment the learner is simply informed how well or badly they has performed.. In correction some specific information is provided on aspects of the learners performance, through explanation or provision of better alternatives. Principle correction should include information on what the learner did right ,as well as wrong, and why ?

Paul Black and Dylan William found that student feedback is likely to have a greater impact on academic performance than any other single factor (Black and William 1998). This formative assesment, in their opinion, "lies at the guts of effective learning." They primarily based this assumption on a detailed reading of the scientific evidence they have. It is important to ensure that the feedback we provide is appropriate for the learners and the activities they are involved in, and that we recognize the feedback as a critical part of the learning process.

Most teachers acknowledge feedback in terms of its motivational value, the value of positive feedback, and negative incentives that can generate negative reinforcement. Beyond the motivational aspects of feedback, teachers have linguistic and cognitive reasons to think carefully about how they respond. Jordan (1993). As Smith said, "A language learner is an active and selective collector of information, receiving and interpreting new information based on rules already stored in the brain. Teacher feedback will result in minor changes to the original hypothesis.

All students make mistakes at various stages of their language learning. It is a part of the natural process they are going

through and occurs for a number of reasons. Students' own language can get in the way. This is most obvious in the case of "false friend" - words that sound or look the same but mean something different, such as "assistir" in Spanish, which means "to be present" in English, not "to help." False friends are more common where the target language shares a common heritage with English. Intervention by students' own language is not the only reason for error. There is a category that many call developmental mistakes. These are the results of conscious or subconscious processing, which often over-generalizes the rule, for example, when a student, having learned to say things like "I must leave," then begins to say "I must leave," without realizing that the use of "To" is not allowed with must. (Jordan RR 1997) Some mistakes are deep seated and need constant attention, with the help of language feedback the teacher responses to the lerners produce. In its most narrow definition, this refers to teacher response to error. Correcting these mistakes is a vital part of the teacher's role and what the teacher is uniquely capable of delivering, but precisely because it involves pointing out people's mistakes, we must be careful when correcting, because if we do it intensely, we can frustrate our students and undermine their confidence. How we respond to students when they speak in class will go a long way not only in how well they perform on assignments, but also on how they behave in future assignments. We also need to respond to the content, not just the language form, we need to be able to unravel the problems our students are facing, but we may well decide to do this after the event, and not during it.

Our tolerance for error in a task session will be much higher than during a more controlled session. If communication is completely interrupted during class, we may have to intervene. We can also ask students to help or correct each other. This works well where there is a genuine collaborative atmosphere, the idea of a group helping all of its members is a powerful concept, but it can nonetheless go completely wrong if the person making the mistake feels humiliated by the process by thinking that he himself is the only one who does not know grammar or vocabulary. Here we need to be extremely sensitive, encouraging technique only where it does not undermine such students. As we said above, it is worth asking students what they think about which methods they personally feel comfortable with.

Correction usually consists of two separate stages. In the first, teachers show students that a mistake was made, in the second, they help students to do something about it if necessary. The first set of tricks we need to know about is about detecting incorrectness. These methods are only really useful for what we think of as language "misspellings" and not as built-in or systematic errors. When we show inaccuracy, we hope that students can correct themselves as soon as the problem is pointed out. If they cannot do this, we will need to move on to alternative methods.

Conclusion

Correction helps students to clarify their understanding of the meaning and construction of the language. This is a vital part of the teacher's role and something

that the teacher can provide uniquely, but precisely because it includes pointing out people's mistakes, we must be careful when correcting, because if we do this intensely, we can upset our students and undermine their confidence. Correction of language mistakes is utter important, our problem is how to do this without conveying the message that they are the only or main basis for judging what has been written. One possibility is to mark corrections in the text and devote comments at the end to the organization of the content, followed by evaluation. Alternatively, we can correct errors and make suggestions for content and organization, but not rate and grade only on the basis of the rewritten revised

version. We have to be extremely sensitive about the way we give feedback and the way we correct. This means not reacting to absolutely every mistake that a student makes if this will demotivate that particular student. It means judging just the right moment to correct, Taking into account the preferences of the group and of individual students. In communicative or fluency activities it means deciding if and when to intervene at all, and we do, what is the best way to do it. If we have time, we should talk to our students about feedback and corrections and explain to them what we are going to do, when and why, and then offer their own comments so that we can make a deal with them about this aspect of classroom learning.

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